

To Compare the Maternal and Perinatal Outcome in Pregnant Women with and without Thyroid Disorder

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Received: 04-02-2023 / Revised: 11-03-2023 / Accepted: 10-04-2023

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: After diabetes mellitus, thyroid disorders are among the most prevalent endocrine conditions in pregnant women. Several changes in the mother's thyroid function are seen during pregnancy & thyroid dysfunction occurs from failing to adjust to these physiological changes. It is generally known that subclinical thyroid dysfunction, in addition to overt thyroid dysfunction, also negatively affects the mother and the foetus and can cause preterm birth, abortion, preeclampsia, eclampsia, placental abruption, low birth weight, and neonatal hypothyroidism. Thyroid hormone availability issues may also affect a fetus's capacity to grow cognitively and neurologically.

Aim of the Study: To compare the maternal and perinatal outcome in pregnant women with and without thyroid disorder.

Materials and Methods: This is a prospective study conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Sri Siddhartha Medical College and Hospital, Tumakuru from February 2021 to July 2022 in 160 patients.

Results: In this study, among the 80 cases of thyroid disorder, 75% (60/80) cases were Hypothyroid and 25% (20/80) cases were Hyperthyroid. Anemia (mild-moderate) was most common complication with p value-0.114, which is not significant. 2nd most common complication being preterm labor with p value – 0.710, which is not significant.

Conclusion: In this study of thyroid disorder in pregnancy, showed no significant association between the maternal and perinatal complication in patients with thyroid disorder. As our hospital is a referral center and receive many complicated cases, results cannot be generalized to the whole population and it needs further studies.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, fetal Outcome, Maternal Outcome.

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Introduction

Thyroid disorders are is linked to difficulties for both the mother and the foetus and is the

2nd most prevalent endocrinological disorder during pregnancy.

Hyperthyroidism occurs in 0.1 to 0.4% of pregnant women. [1] Excess thyroxine may cause miscarriage or preterm birth. In untreated women or in those who remain hyperthyroid despite therapy, incidences of preeclampsia, heart failure, and adverse perinatal outcomes are higher like and prolonged jaundice, poor feeding, transient hypothermia, failure to gain weight, constipation 12-fold greater risk of delivering an infant with hearing loss.[2,3]

About 2-3% of pregnant women are hypothyroid of whom 0.3-0.5% have overt hypothyroidism and about 2-2.5% of them present with subclinical hypothyroidism according to the western literature, while in India prevalence rates ranges from 4.8% to 11%.[2] Thyroid auto immunity appears to be associated with an increased risk of miscarriage and preterm delivery. Adverse maternal & perinatal outcomes are preeclampsia, placental abruption, low birth weight baby, preterm still birth. Most experts agree that adequate hormone replacement during pregnancy minimizes the risk of adverse outcomes and most complications. [3]

HCG produced by placenta is homologous to TSH and has some TSH like activity. Maternal thyroid axis changes during pregnancy resulting in increase in ft_4 levels and they remain high until birth. Maternal thyrotoxicosis causes congenital hypothyroidism. [4]

Aim of the Study

To compare the maternal and perinatal outcome in pregnant women with and without thyroid disorder.

Its Objectives:

To assess maternal and perinatal outcome in pregnant women with thyroid disorder

To assess maternal and perinatal outcome in euthyroid pregnancies

To compare the maternal and perinatal outcome in pregnant women with thyroid disorder with euthyroid pregnancy group.

Materials And Methods

This is a prospective study conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Sri Siddhartha Medical College and Hospital, Tumakuru from February 2021 to July 2022 after getting the approval from the Ethical Committee among the women admitted in department of OBG as per the inclusion and exclusion criteria after proper counselling and after getting their consent, participants divided into 2 groups, Group A :78 participants were euthyroid pregnant women and Group B : 78 participants were pregnant women with thyroid disorder and followed up till the end of their pregnancy

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All pregnant women

Exclusion criteria:

1. women having multiple gestation,
2. Major obstetrical complications like antepartum haemorrhage, malnutrition, hydramnios.
3. systemic disease like cardiac, renal, liver disease
4. Intake of drugs like steroids, amiodarone, methadone, dopamine.

Maternal and perinatal outcomes were noted and compared in both the groups.

To measure the serum TSH level, patient samples were provided. ft_3 and ft_4 levels were assessed if serum TSH values were abnormal. reference ranges of American Thyroid Association's Guidelines for the Diagnosis and Management of Thyroid Disease During Pregnancy and Postpartum, were used in this study.

The following reference values for normal serum TSH were suggested by ATA Regulation 14.2:

1st trimester – 0.1 to 2.5 m IU/L,
 2nd trimester – 0.2 to 3.0 m IU/L and
 3 rd trimester – 0.3 to 3.0 m IU/L.

Normal free T4 and free T3 levels range from 0.7 to 1.8 ng/ml and 1.7 to 4.2 pg/ml, respectively. Patients were divided into categories based on their hormonal values: high serum TSH level accompanied by normal fT4, fT3 is considered as subclinical hypothyroidism. Overt hypothyroidism is defined as a high serum TSH level with fT4 and fT3 levels that are below normal. Low serum TSH level with normal fT3, fT4 is considered subclinical hyperthyroidism. Overt hyperthyroidism: Low serum TSH level with higher-than-normal levels of fT3 and fT4.

Sub clinical/ overt hypothyroid cases were treated with Thyroxine. Sub clinical / overt hyperthyroid cases were treated with Propylthiouracyl. Every 4 weeks, TSH level was estimated and the dose of the drug was adjusted. Outcomes of the pregnancy were followed up and documented. The following outcome variables of the pregnancy in

relation to the thyroid disorders were studied: Preeclampsia, Abruptio placenta, Preterm delivery, IUGR, Low birth weight, Stillbirth, Abortion.

Results And Observation

Results were analysed based on the following

Basic variable:

1. Age of the patient
2. Parity of the patient (obstetric score)
3. BMI of the patient
4. Past obstetric history

Outcome variable:

1. Mode of delivery
2. Maternal complications
3. Neonatal outcomes

Analysis of Results

In the present study among cases 75% (60/80) cases were Hypothyroid and 25% (20/80) cases were Hyperthyroid. Among Controls 80% (80/80) patients were Euthyroid.

Table 1: Age distribution

Age distribution	Cases	Controls
<20 years	05 (6.25 %)	06(7.5%)
20-25 years	30(37.5%)	29(36.25 %)
26-30 years	35(43.75%)	34(42.5 %)
>30 years	10(12.5 %)	11(13.75 %)
Total	80(100%)	80(100 %)

In both study groups majority of study subjects were in the age group of 26 – 30 years and 2nd largest age group is between 20 – 25 years in both study groups.

Table 2: Parity distribution

Parity distribution	Cases	Controls
Primigravida	49(61.2 %)	43(53.75 %)
Gravida 2	19(23.8%)	20(25%)
Multi gravida	12 (15%)	17 (21.25%)
Total	80 (100%)	80 (100 %)

In this study, majority were primigravida in both study groups 49/80 (61.2 %) in cases and 43/80 (53.75 %) in control group. Next majority were 2nd gravida in both groups, being 19/80 (23.8%) in cases and 20/80 (25%) in controls.

Table 3: Distribution of Thyroid Status

Thyroid status	CASES
Hypothyroid	60(75%)
Hyperthyroidism	20(25 %)
Total	80(100%)

In the present study among cases 60/80 (75%) cases were Hypothyroid and 20/80(25%) cases were Hyperthyroid. Among Controls 80/80 (100%) patients were Euthyroid .

Table 4: Distribution of Hypothyroidism In Cases

Hypothyroidism	Cases	Percentage
Subclinical hypothyroidism	35	58.3
Overt hypothyroidism	25	41.7
Total	60	100%

In the present study among hypothyroidism cases 35/80 (58.3%) were having Subclinical hypothyroidism and 25/80 (41.7%) were having Overt hypothyroidism.

Table 5: Distribution of Past History

Past history	CASES	CONTROLS
Previous BOH	10 (12.5%)	5 (6.3%)
Previous abortion	12(15 %)	10(12.5 %)
Previous Neonatal death	02(2.5%)	0
No significant past history	56 (70%)	65(81.2 %)
Total	80(100%)	80(100%)

In the present study among cases Previous BOH was seen in 10/80 (12.5%) subjects, Previous abortion in 12/80 (15%) patients, Previous Neonatal deaths in 2/80 (2.5%) and No significant past history in 56/80 (70%) subjects.

Among controls Previous BOH was seen in 5/80 (6.3 %) subjects, Previous abortion in 10/80 (12.5%) subjects, No significant past history in 65/80 (81.2%) subjects.

Table 6: Distribution By BMI

Weight	CASES	CONTROLS
BMI <25	58 (72.5%)	62(77.5 %)
BMI 26-30	16(20%)	16(20%)
BMI >30	6(7.5 %)	2(2.5%)
Total	80(100%)	80(100%)

In the this study majority of study subjects are of BMI <25 kg/m². Being 58/80 (72.5%) in cases and 62/80 (77.5%) in controls. 2nd largest BMI group comprised of BMI between 26 -30kg/m² being 16/80 (20%) in cases as well as in control group. Least number of patients were noted with BMI >30 kg/m² , being 6/80 (7.5%) in cases and 2/80 (2.5%) in controls.

Table 7: Mode of Pregnancy Termination

Mode of Termination of Pregnancy	Cases	Controls
OTHERS	50(62.5 %)	52(65 %)
LSCS	30(37.5%)	28(35 %)
Total	80(100 %)	80(100%)

(OTHERS INCLUDE 40 vaginal delivery, 8 abortion and 2 instrumental delivery in cases, in controls 46 vaginal delivery , 5 abortions and 1 instrumental delivery).

In the present study majority of the subjects delivered by spontaneous vaginal delivery , being 40/80 (50%) in cases and 46/80 (57.5%) in control group. Next majority delivered by LSCS being 30/80 (37.5%) cases and 28/80 (35%) were from control group. And the least number of subjects delivered by assisted vaginal/ instrumental delivery, being 2/80 (2.5%) in cases and 1/80 (1.3%) in control group.

Table 8: Distribution of Maternal Complications

Maternal complications	CASES	CONTROLS
PIH	17 (21.2%)	22(27.5%)
Anemia (mild-moderate)	50(62.5%)	40(50%)
Abortion	8(10%)	5(6.25%)
Preterm labour	20(25 %)	18(22.5%)
LBW	8(10%)	4(5%)
IUGR	10(12.5%)	8(10%)
IUD	1(1.25 %)	1(1.25%)
PROM	10(12.5%)	11(13.7%)
GDM	8(10%)	10(12.5%)

(**single study subject has more than one complication)

In the present study among cases Anemia (mild-moderate) was most common complication seen in 62.5% (50/80) patients followed by preterm labor in 25% (20/80) patients.

Among controls Anemia (mild-moderate) was most common complication seen in 50% (40/80) patients followed by preterm labor in 22.5% (18/80) patients.

Table 9: Distribution of Perinatal Outcome

Perinatal outcome	CASES	CONTROLS
IUD	1(1.25%)	1(1.25%)
LBW	8(10%)	4(5%)
Open posterior fontanel	10(12.5 %)	5(6.25 %)
Neonatal jaundice (>7days)	0	0
No complication	32 (40%)	60 (77.5%)
Total	80(100%)	80(100 %)

In the present study, among cases IUD noted in 1.25% (1/80), LBW noted in 10% (8/80), open posterior fontanel noted in 12.5% (10/80).

Among controls, IUD noted in 1.25% (1/80) LBW noted in 5% (4/80) open posterior fontanel noted in 6.25% (5/80)

Table 10: Distribution of NICU Admission

NICU Admission	Cases	Controls
YES	18 (22.5%)	17(21.2%)
NO	62(77.5 %)	63(78.8%)
Total	80(100 %)	80(100%)

In the present study among cases only 22.5% patients (18/80) required NICU admissions and among controls 21.2% patients (17/80) required NICU admissions.

Statistical Analysis

Case/Control Cross Tabulation

P value significant if its <0.05

Maternal Complications	Cases (Yes)	(No)	Controls (Yes)	(No)	Chi Square Value	P-VALUE
PIH	17	63	21	59	0.5522	0.457
Anaemia	50	30	40	40	2.54	0.114
Abortion	8	72	5	75	0.7535	0.385
Lscs	30	50	28	52	0.109	0.742
Pre-Term Labour	20	60	18	62	0.138	0.710
Lbw	8	72	4	76	1.44	0.230
Iugr	10	70	8	72	0.2504	0.617
Iud	1	79	1	79	0	1.000
Prom	10	70	11	69	0.0548	0.815
Gdm	8	72	10	70	0.2504	0.617
Open Post. Fontanel	10	70	5	75	1.84	0.18
NICU admissions	18	62	17	63	0.036	0.848

Statistical Analysis of Thyroid Levels

	Cases (mean +/- SD)	Controls (mean +/- SD)
TSH-LEVELS	7.222+/-3.237	2.620 +/--1.040
Free-T3	326.9 +/--228.7	200+/-67.50
Free-T4	28.60 +/- 17.549	20.34 +/- 5.051

Discussion

Maternal Outcome variables	Other Studies	Present study
Mode of termination of pregnancy – lscs	24% -Vandana <i>et al</i> [5]	37.5%
PIH	14.7% - Sree latha <i>et al</i> study[6] 1.9% -Daniel <i>et al</i> study	21.2%
Anemia	4.2% -Sree latha <i>et al</i> study	62.5%
Abortion	2.1% -Sree latha <i>et al</i> study 26.7%- Subhash <i>et al</i>	10%
Preterm labour	3.1% -Sree latha <i>et al</i> study 14.03% -Tuija <i>et al</i> [7]	25 %
GDM	4.25%- Sree latha <i>et al</i> study	10%
IUGR	0.5% - Daniel <i>et al</i> study	12.5%
IUD	1.1% - pu yu su <i>et al</i> [8]	1.25 %
PROM	2.9% - Tuija <i>et al</i>	12.5%
Fetal Outcome variables		

LBW	16.32% - Hareesh MV <i>et al</i> [9] 25% - Ajmani Sangeeta <i>et al</i> [10]	10%
Open posterior fontanel	3.3%- Subhash <i>et al</i>	12.5 %
Neonatal jaundice	0- Singh B <i>et al</i>	0
NICU ADMISSION	14.28% -Dharasingh Meena <i>et al</i> [11]	22.5%

Conclusion

This study showed no association between thyroid disorder and adverse maternal & perinatal outcomes. As this is not a randomized control trial, more well controlled studies are needed to conclude the same. Until then we recommend to follow ACOG &ATA guidelines and screen all ANC cases for thyroid disorders in first trimester by doing serum TSH as first line investigation, irrespective of previous disease status. All pregnant women should receive prompt treatment for thyroid disorder at the earliest for optimal maternal and fetal outcome.

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